

Study of Friedel-Crafts acylation and Baeyer-Villiger oxidation reactions on benzocycloheptanones and 1-tetralones in acid media

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Abstract : Synthesis and characterization of some new substituted naphthopyrones (2a-d) and 4,5-dihydro-3H-benzo[b]oxocin/oxepin-2-ones (3a-d), starting from 1-tetralone and benzocycloheptanones have been reported. Biological testing of these compounds for their antimicrobial activity has been carried out.

Keywords : Friedel-Crafts acylation, Baeyer-Villiger oxidation, naphthopyrones, antimicrobial activity, synthesis.

Introduction

Various pyrano, pyrazino and quinolino derivatives were found to exhibit a variety of pharmacological activities¹⁻¹⁰. Promoted by these observations and in continuation of our interest on the synthesis of biologically active nitrogen and sulfur containing heterocycles¹¹⁻¹⁴, here we report the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of substituted naphthopyrones (2a-d) and 4,5-dihydro-3H-benzo[b]oxocin/oxepine-2-ones (3a-d), members of novel, hitherto unknown benzocycloheptanones and tetralone systems respectively.

Results and discussion

(A) *Friedel-Crafts reaction* : In order to achieve our objective, 3-methyl/2,3-dimethylbenzocycloheptan-5-one¹⁵ (1a-b) and 7-methyl/6,7-dimethyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-naphthalene-1-one¹⁶ (1c-d) were treated with a mixture of glacial acetic acid and polyphosphoric acid at 100 °C to produce 2,10-dimethyl/2,9,10-trimethylbenzo[6,7]-cyclohepta[b]pyran-4-one (2a-b) and 2,9-dimethyl/2,8,9-trimethyl-5,6-dihydronaphthopyran-4-one (2c-d). The IR spectrum of 2 showed strong absorption band at 1650 cm⁻¹ (C=O). The ¹H NMR spectrum of 2 also showed the presence of methyl protons as singlets at δ 2.25, one proton at δ 6.10 as singlet corresponding to the 3H proton in pyran ring and the other methylene protons appeared as a multiplets at δ 2.00-2.10, 2.20-2.30 and 2.45-2.50 respectively.

(B) *Baeyer-Villiger oxidation* : Oxidation of ketones with hydrogen peroxide or with a peroxy acid results in

their conversion into esters. Whereas cyclic ketones are converted into lactones¹⁷. Thus, the compound 1 was treated with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in a cold dichloromethane to produce 9-methyl/8,9-dimethyl-3,4,5,6-tetrahydro-2H-benzo[b]oxocin-2-one (3a-b) and 8-methyl/7,8-dimethyl-4,5-dihydro-3H-benzo[b]oxepin-2-one (3c-d). The IR spectrum of 3 showed the characteristic band at 1740 cm⁻¹ due to lactone functionality. The structures of compounds 3a-d were assigned on the basis of the ¹H NMR spectra. The structure of compounds 2a-d and 3a-d was further confirmed by elemental analysis and mass spectra.

For 1-3

a, n = 2, R¹ = CH₃, R² = H; b, n = 2, R¹ = R² = CH₃;

c, n = 1, R¹ = CH₃, R² = H; d, n = 1, R¹ = R² = CH₃

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were determined using Gallankamp apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a FT-IR 1605 Perkin-Elmer, ^1H NMR spectra in CDCl_3 on a Varian FT-80A spectrometer with TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a VG-micromass 7070H mass spectrometer. TLC was run on silica gel G coated plates using iodine vapour as visualizing agent.

Synthesis of 2,10-dimethyl/2,9,10-trimethylbenzo[6,7]-cyclohepta[b]pyran-4-one (2a-b) and 2,9-dimethyl/2,8,9-trimethyl-5,6-dihydro-naphthopyran-4-one (2c-d) :

General procedure : A mixture of compound 1 (0.001 mol), acetic acid (0.002 mol) and freshly prepared polyphosphoric acid (40 g, 2 : 1 ratio of P_2O_5 and H_3PO_4) was heated at 100 °C for 6–8 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured into ice water and extracted with chloroform, concentrated *in vacuo* and chromatographed over silica gel with ethyl acetate-petroleum ether as eluent (1 : 7) to produce 2a. Yield : 80%; m.p. 132–135 °C; IR (KBr) : 1652 cm^{-1} (C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.00–2.10 (2H, m, 6- CH_2), 2.20–2.30 (2H, m, 7- CH_2), 2.25 (6H, s, 2 and 10- CH_3), 2.50–2.60 (2H, m, 5- CH_2), 6.10 (1H, s, 3H), 7.05–7.30 (3H, m, Ar-H); MS : m/z 240 (M^{+}) (Found : C, 79.05; H, 6.62; O, 13.30). $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 80.00; H, 6.66; O, 13.33%.

Compound 2b : Yield : 81%; m.p. 128–130 °C; IR (KBr) : 1650 cm^{-1} (C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.10–2.20 (2H, m, 6- CH_2), 2.20–2.38 (2H, m, 7- CH_2), 2.28 (9H, s, 2, 9 and 10- CH_3), 2.50–2.60 (2H, m, 5- CH_2), 6.15 (1H, s, 3-H), 7.10 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.30 (1H, s, Ar-H); MS : m/z 254 (M^{+}) (Found : C, 80.28; H, 7.04; O, 12.54). $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 80.31; H, 7.08; O, 12.59%.

Compound 2c : Yield : 85%; m.p. 107–130 °C; IR (KBr) : 1652 cm^{-1} (C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.38 (6H, s, 2 and 9- CH_3), 2.70–2.85 (2H, m, 6- CH_2), 2.85–2.95 (2H, m, 5- CH_2), 6.20 (1H, s, 3-H), 7.15–7.63 (3H, m, Ar-H); MS : m/z 226 (M^{+}) (Found : C, 79.61; H, 6.15; O, 14.13). $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 79.64; H, 6.19; O, 14.15%.

Compound 2d : Yield : 83%; m.p. 105–107 °C; IR (KBr) : 1650 cm^{-1} (C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 2.10–2.20 (2H, m, 6- CH_2), 2.25 (9H, s, 2, 8 and 9- CH_3), 2.70–2.95 (2H, m, 7- CH_2), 6.17 (1H, s, 3-H), 7.00 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.38 (1H, s, Ar-H); MS : m/z 240 (M^{+}) (Found : C, 79.08; H, 6.62; O, 13.30). $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 80.00; H, 6.66; O, 13.33%.

Synthesis of 9-methyl/8,9-dimethyl-3,4,5,6-tetrahydro-2H-benzo[b]oxocin-2-one (3a-b) and 8-methyl/7,8-dimethyl-4,5-dihydro-3H-benzo[b]oxepin-2-one (3c-d) :

General procedure : A mixture of compound 1 (0.0005 mol) and MCPBA (0.002 mol) in cold dichloromethane solution was stirred at room temperature for 24 h. The reaction mixture was neutralized with sodium carbonate and extracted with chloroform, concentrated *in vacuo* and chromatographed over silica gel with ethyl acetate-petroleum ether as eluent (1 : 9) to produce 3a : Yield : 78%; m.p. 250 °C; IR (KBr) : 1741 cm^{-1} (C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 1.75–1.80 (2H, m, 4- CH_2), 1.82–1.95 (2H, m, 5- CH_2), 2.10–2.30 (2H, m, 6- CH_2), 2.20 (3H, s, 9- CH_3), 2.35–2.45 (2H, m, 3- CH_2), 6.80–7.50 (3H, m, Ar-H); MS : m/z 190 (M^{+}) (Found : C, 75.73; H, 7.32; O, 16.80). $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 75.78; H, 7.36; O, 16.84%.

Compound 3b : Yield : 80%; m.p. 98–100 °C; IR (KBr) : 1732 cm^{-1} (C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_2) : δ 1.70–1.81 (2H, m, 4- CH_2), 1.82–2.00 (2H, m, 5- CH_2), 2.20–2.38 (2H, m, 6- CH_2), 2.28 (6H, s, 8 and 9- CH_3), 2.42–2.60 (2H, m, 3- CH_2), 6.90 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.23 (1H, s, Ar-H); MS : m/z 204 (M^{+}) (Found : C, 76.43; H, 7.80; O, 15.63). $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 76.47; H, 7.84; O, 15.68%.

Compound 3c : Yield : 78%; m.p. 110–112 °C; IR (KBr) : 1731 cm^{-1} (C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 1.60–1.80 (2H, m, 4- CH_2), 2.25 (3H, s, 7 and 8- CH_3), 2.25–2.40 (2H, m, 5- CH_2), 2.50–2.70 (2H, m, 3- CH_2), 6.50–7.40 (3H, m, Ar-H); MS : m/z 176 (M^{+}) (Found : C, 69.95; H, 6.87; O, 18.14). $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 75.00; H, 6.81; O, 18.18%.

Compound 3d : Yield : 81%; m.p. 107–109 °C; IR (KBr) : 1735 cm^{-1} (C=O); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 1.60–1.80 (2H, m, 4- CH_2), 2.25 (6H, s, 7 and 8- CH_3), 2.25–2.40 (2H, m, 5- CH_2), 2.50–2.70 (2H, m, 3- CH_2), 6.50 (1H, s, Ar-H), 6.85 (1H, s, Ar-H); MS : m/z 190 (M^{+}) (Found : C, 75.74; H, 7.33; O, 16.80). $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 75.78; H, 7.36; O, 16.84%.

Biological evaluation :

(a) *Antimicrobial activity :* All the compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity at a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{well}$ in agar media¹⁸ using Rifapicin in antibacterial and Clotrimazole in antifungal activity as reference compounds. Compounds 2a, 2b, 2c and 2d showed maximum activity in terms of diameter of the zone of inhibition (8 mm) as compared with Rifampicin

(13 mm) against gram +ve bacterium *Staphylococcus*. All the compounds were found to be resistant towards gram -ve bacterium *E. coli*. All compounds are ineffective against the fungus *Trichoderma species*.

(b) *Analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities* : Analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities of the compounds were determined by Tumer¹⁹ writhing test²⁰ and rat-paw edema test²¹. The inhibition of the edema was recorded on a plethysmometer (UGO BASILE make) and expressed as % inhibition. Compounds 2a, 2b, 2c and 2d showed maximum inhibition 30–32% and 3a, 3b, 3c and 3d showed less inhibition in rats while aspirin and phenylbutazone at the same dose (100 mg/kg, P.O.) produced 17% and 39% inhibition of 1% carrageenan induced inflammation, respectively.

Compounds exhibited significant anti-inflammatory activity better than aspirin but comparable with that of phenylbutazone. However, they were found to possess less analgesic with reference to aspirin.

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